

Step	Prep	Machine	Post	Max n	Notes
Cover back					
Mount to 6" CW, 2pcs double side tape on edge		3		1	
<i>E-beam 4: deposit Cr 2500A @ 4A/s</i>	15	120	15	5	
Demount and inspect		3		1	
Scribe wafer number SW corner front					
PR layer 0					
Inspect, N2 clean				1	
Bake 135C 30" cool					
DUV42 3500rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 220C 60" cool					
UV6 -.8					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 135C 60" cool	10	5n	10	6	
Inspect back					
Load into ASML					
<i>ASML: Layer 0 (PM)</i>		10+2n		25	PM marks only (42, {-5 0 5}) on all sides
Bake 135C 90" cool		2		4	
AZ300MIF 45"		2		6	
Rinse in DI					
Dry					
Inspect all E and W PMs					
Etch layer 0					
Insert 4" carrier into SLR		5			
<i>SLR: Flow O2/Ar Clean</i>		10			Use needle to set He to >3 sccm
N2 glass wafer then load in SLR					
<i>SLR: Flow AR+124nm+PR</i>	5	13n	5	1	
Strip layer 0					
NMP 80C 60'	10	60		6	
Rinse with NMP, spin NMP+ACE+ISO+N2 both sides		5		1	
O2 asher 2' 200W					
Inspect all E and W PMs	5	2n			
PR layer 1					
Inspect, N2 clean				1	

Bake 135C 30" cool					
DUV42 3500rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 220C 60" cool					
UV6 -.8 3500rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 135C 60" cool	10	5n	10	6	
Inspect back					
Load into ASML					
ASML: Layer 1 (A)		10+2n			4x overlapping exposure
Bake 135C 90" cool		2		4	
AZ300MIF 45"		2		6	
Rinse in DI					
Dry					
Inspect all E and W PMs, grating					
Etch layer 1					
Insert 4" carrier into SLR		5			
SLR: Flow O2/Ar Clean		10			Use needle to set He to >3 sccm
N2 glass wafer then load in SLR					
SLR: Flow AR+145nm+PR	5	13n	5	1	
Strip layer 1					
NMP 80C 60'	10	60		6	
Rinse with NMP, spin NMP+ACE+ISO+N2 both sides		5		1	
O2 asher 2' 200W					
Inspect all E and W PMs, grating	5	2n			
PR layer 2					
Inspect, N2 clean				1	
Bake 135C 30" cool					
DUV42 3500rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 220C 60" cool					
UV6 -.8 3500rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 135C 60" cool	10	5n	10	6	
Inspect back					

Load into ASML					
<i>ASML: Layer 2 (B)</i>		10+2n			4x overlapping exposure
Bake 135C 90" cool		2		4	
AZ300MIF 45"		2		6	
Rinse in DI					
Dry					
Inspect all E and W PMs, verify layer alignment					
Etch layer 2					
Insert 4" carrier into SLR		5			
<i>SLR: Flow O2/Ar Clean</i>		10			Use needle to set He to >3 sccm
N2 glass wafer then load in SLR					
<i>SLR: Flow AR+289nm+PR</i>	5	13n	5	1	
Strip layer 2					
NMP 80C 60'	10	60		6	
Rinse with NMP, spin NMP+ACE+ISO+N2 both sides		5		1	
O2 asher 2' 200W					
Inspect all E and W PMs	5	2n			
PR layer 3					
Inspect, N2 clean				1	
Bake 135C 30" cool					
DUV42 3500rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 220C 60" cool					
UV6 -.8 2000rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 135C 60" cool	10	5n	10	6	
Inspect back					
Load into ASML					
<i>ASML: Layer 3 @</i>		10+2n			4x overlapping exposure
Bake 135C 90" cool		2		4	
AZ300MIF 45"		2		6	
Rinse in DI					
Dry					
Verify layer alignment					
Etch layer 3					

Insert 4" carrier into SLR		5			
SLR: Flow O2/Ar Clean		10			Use needle to set He to >3 sccm
N2 glass wafer then load in SLR					
SLR: Flow AR+578nm+PR	5	13n	5	1	
AFM finished grating					
Protective PR					
Inspect, N2 clean					
Bake 135C 30" cool					
DUV42 3500rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 220C 60" cool					
UV6 -.8 2000rpm					
Clean back ACE+ISO+N2					
Bake 135C 60" cool					
Cut	30	30n	30		
Finish					
Cr strip until clear					
Cr strip 3'					
NMP 80C 60'					
Rinse with NMP, change NMP					
NMP 80C 60'					
O2 asher 5' 200W					